

JAVASCRIPT OPERATORLARI

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda JavaScript dasturlash tili operatorlari va ularning ifoda va shartlarni yaratishdagi roli muhokama qilinadi. Biz har xil turdagi ma'lumotlarga ega operatorlarning ishlash xususiyatlarini va ulardan turli vaziyatlarda foydalanishni o'rganamiz. Operatorlardan foydalanishda yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan xatolar va ularni oldini olish yo'llari ham ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: JavaScript, operatorlar, ifodalar, mantiq, shartlar.

Аннотация: В этой тезис обсуждаются операторы языка программирования JavaScript и их роль в создании выражений и условий. Изучаются характеристики производительности операторов с разными типами данных и их использование в разных ситуациях. Также рассмотрены возможные ошибки в использовании операторов и способы их избежать.

Ключевые слова: JavaScript, операторы, выражения, логика, условия.

Abstract: This thesis thesis JavaScript programming language operators and their role in creating expressions and conditions. We study the performance characteristics of operators with different types of data and their use in different situations. Possible errors in the use of operators and ways to avoid them are also considered.

Keywords: JavaScript, operators, expressions, logic, conditions.

JavaScript - bu asosan veb-saytlar va veb-ilovalarni yaratish uchun ishlatiladigan dasturlash tili. Operatorlar JavaScript dasturlash tilining muhim elementi hisoblanadi, chunki ular ma'lumotlar ustida turli amallarni bajarishga va muayyan operatsiyalarni bajarish uchun sharoit yaratishga imkon beradi.

JavaScript- da bir necha turdagi bayonotlar mavjud, masalan:

Arifmetik operatorlar Arifmetik operatorlar matematik amallarni bajarish uchun ishlatiladi. JavaScript -da quyidagi arifmetik operatorlar mavjud : qo'shish (+), ayirish (-), ko'paytirish (*), bo'lish (/) va modul (%). Masalan :

```
let x =5;
```

```
let y =2;
```

```
console . log ( x + y ); // natija: 7
```

```
console . log ( x - y ); // natija: 3
```

```
console . log ( x * y ); // natija: 10
```

```
console . log ( x / y ); // natija: 2.5
```

```
console . log ( x % y ); // natija: 1
```

Taqqoslash operatorlari Taqqoslash operatorlari qiymatlarni solishtirish uchun ishlatiladi. JavaScript -da quyidagi taqqoslash operatorlari mavjud : teng (==), teng emas (!=), qat'iy tenglik (===), qat'iy tengsizlik (!==), katta (>), kichik (<), dan katta yoki teng (>=) va kichik yoki teng (<=). Masalan :

```
let x = 5 bo'lsin ;
```

```
let y = 2 bo'lsin ;
```

```
console.log(x == y); // natija : noto'g'ri
console.log( x != y); // natija : rost
console.log(x === '5'); // natija : noto'g'ri
console. log( x !== '5'); // natija : rost
console logi (x > y); // natija : rost
console logi (x < y); // natija : noto'g'ri
console.log(x >= y); // natija : rost
console.log(x <= y); // natija : noto'g'ri
```

Mantiqiy operatorlar Mantiqiy operatorlar shartlarni ulash uchun ishlatiladi. JavaScript- da quyidagi mantiqiy operatorlar mavjud : AND operatori (&&), OR operatori (||) va NOT operatori (!). Masalan :

```
let x = 5 bo'lsin ;
let y = 2 bo'lsin ;
console. log(x > 3 && y < 4); // natija : rost
console.log(x > 3 || y > 4); // natija : rost
console.log( !(x > 3)); // natija : noto'g'ri
```

O'stirish va kamaytirish operatorlari: o'sish va kamaytirish operatorlari o'zgaruvchining qiymatini 1 ga oshirish yoki kamaytirish uchun ishlatiladi. quyidagi oshirish va kamaytirish operatorlari JavaScript da mavjud : oshirish (++) va kamaytirish (--). Masalan :

```
let x = 5 bo'lsin ;
console logi (x++); // natija : 5
console . log ( x ); // natija: 6
console . log ( ++ x ); // natija: 7
console . log ( x- ); // natija: 7
console . log ( x ); // natija: 6
console log ( --x); // natija : 5
```

Shartli (uchlik) operator Shartli operator (uchlik operator) kodning bir qatorida shartlar yaratish uchun ishlatiladi. U quyidagi sintaksisga ega: shart ? qiymat1: qiymat2. Agar shart rost bo'lsa, qiymat1 qaytariladi, aks holda qiymat2 qaytariladi. Masalan:

```
let yosh = 25;
let status = yosh >= 18 bo'lsin ? " Voyaga etgan ": " Voyaga etmagan ";
console . log ( holat ); // natija: "kattalar"
```

JavaScript tilidagi operatorlar dasturlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Operatorlardan to'g'ri foydalanish kodni soddalashtirish va uning samaradorligini oshirish imkonini beradi.

Xulosa

Ushbu tezisda biz JavaScript dasturlash tilining arifmetik, taqqoslash operatorlari, mantiqiy operatorlar, belgilash operatorlari, oshirish va kamaytirish operatorlari, uchlik operatorlari kabi asosiy operatorlarini ko'rib chiqdik . Biz ularning sintaksisi va qo'llanilishini o'rganib chiqdik va ularning dasturlashdagi rolini muhokama qildik.

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